

Exploring Parabolic Patterns in the Map of Integers and Divisors (MID) Framework

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Abstract: The Map of Integers and Divisors (MID) serves as a compelling visual paradigm, illustrating the complex interplay between integers and their divisors through a two-factor factorization landscape. This study extends our previous exploration of the MID's parabolic patterns, delving deeper into the arithmetic and geometric nuances manifested within the framework. We introduce the concept of SOM Zones—sequential zones demarcated by square, oblong, and (square minus 1) numbers—whose sizes increase linearly and pervade the numerical line.

Through meticulous analysis, we delineate the symbiotic relationship between divisors and these zones, using these connections to elucidate the prime number distribution along the numerical continuum. We investigate the reasons for the consistent emergence of at least one prime number between a square number and its consecutive oblong and another distinct prime between an oblong number and the subsequent square. These insights have led to the discovery of several novel prime number sieves—unprecedented in the literature—including SPM6: A Geometric Sieve of Prime Numbers in the MID Based on Multiples of 6, The MID Circles Sieve of Primes (MCSP), The MID Squares Sieve of Primes (MSSP), The MID Integers plus Divisors Sieve of Primes (MIPSP), and The MID Prime Integers minus Divisors Sieve (MIMSP).

These sieves lay the groundwork for a forthcoming study that expands upon these concepts, exploring their implications for the distribution of prime numbers within any polynomial framework. We conclude this preprint with a proposition for a "Factory for Record-Breaking Astronomical Prime Numbers," which leverages oblong numbers and large primorials in a novel methodological approach, setting the stage for potential breakthroughs in prime number discovery.

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1 Introduction

*Life is not fair: each integer has distinct pairs of complementary divisors.
There's more: all integers of value have a finite number of divisors.
The only one that has no value at all has an infinite number of divisors.*

The interrelations of integers and their divisors have been the bedrock of numerous mathematical inquiries, leading to profound insights in number theory. The Map of Integers and Divisors (MID) offers fertile ground for visualizing these relationships, presenting a mathematical tapestry woven with the threads of factorization properties. Within this framework, integers are not mere placeholders on the number line but key players in a geometric landscape rife with patterns and structures.

The previous explorations of the MID have revealed the emergence of parabolic patterns, a visual testament to the underlying mathematical principles that govern the distribution of divisors. This study builds on those findings, introducing the concept of SOM (Square, Oblong, and (square Minus 1) numbers) Zones, which serve as the backdrop for a deeper examination of divisor dynamics and prime number distribution.

In traversing the MID, we encounter zones delineated by square, oblong, and (square minus 1) numbers, each zone expanding linearly and successively. These zones, termed SOM Zones, are not only a visual curiosity but a key to unlocking the distribution of prime numbers along the numerical continuum. Our analysis within these zones reveals a persistent presence of prime numbers between consecutive square and oblong numbers and vice versa, a pattern that had remained elusive until now.

From this vantage point, we have uncovered a suite of innovative prime number sieves—SPM6, MCSP, MSSP, MIPSP, and MIMSP. Each sieve stands as a unique tool, shedding light on the prime number enigma and challenging the traditional bounds of prime discovery methods. Their collective impact provides a nuanced understanding of prime distribution in the MID, a promising frontier in the pursuit of mathematical understanding.

As we extend these methodologies to polynomial structures, we open a new chapter in the exploration of number theory. This study culminates in proposing a Factory for Record-Breaking Astronomical Prime Numbers, leveraging the potential of oblong numbers and vast primorials. It

is a methodological leap forward, suggesting not just incremental steps but giant strides in the quest for prime numbers of any astronomical magnitude.

In this introduction, we embark on a journey through the intricate interplay of integers, divisors, and prime numbers, setting the stage for a comprehensive exploration of the mathematical phenomena within the MID and beyond.

1.1 Abbreviations and Definitions:

- $(d_{c1}; d_{c2})$: Denotes the central pair of complementary divisors such that $x \geq d_{c2} \geq +\sqrt{|x|} \geq d_{c1} \geq 1$, where $d_{c1} * d_{c2} = x = \text{positive integer}$.
- d_{c1} : Denotes the smallest central complementary divisor satisfying $d_{c2} \geq \pm\sqrt{|x|} \geq d_{c1}$, where $x = d_{c1} * d_{c2}$. For positive divisors, d_{c1} corresponds to the sequence at <https://oeis.org/A033676>.
- d_{c2} : Denotes the largest central complementary divisor satisfying $d_{c2} \geq \pm\sqrt{|x|} \geq d_{c1}$, and $x = d_{c1} * d_{c2}$. For positive divisors, d_{c2} corresponds to the sequence at <https://oeis.org/A033677>.
- b_{dm} : Defined as $b_{dm} = d_{c2} - d_{c1}$ saying the difference between the divisors of the central pair of complementary divisors. The sequence for b_{dm} can be found at <https://oeis.org/A056737>.

$$b_{dm} = \text{https://oeis.org/A033677}[x] - \text{https://oeis.org/A033676}[x] = \text{https://oeis.org/A056737}$$
- b_d : Defined as $b_d = d_2 - d_1$ saying the difference between the divisors of the pair of complementary divisors.

1.2 Reference and Further Reading:

The most recent notations in all studies, texts, figures, tables, graphs, etc., are available online at <https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/653023753021234/> or via the link <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10127987>.

2 Square Numbers and (Square-1) Numbers in MID: Understanding Patterns and Relationships

The Map of Integers and Divisors (MID) reveals intriguing connections between square numbers ($x = y^2$) and their predecessors, the (square-1) numbers ($x = y^2 - 1$).

These relationships are best visualized by plotting the parabolas $x = \pm y^2$, which interestingly cover all points representing the central divisors of square numbers within the MID.

Figure 1. C001641 Illustrates the parabolic coverage of red-colored $x = \pm y^2$, encompassing central divisors of square numbers within the MID.

2.1 Periodicity and Connections:

To visualize the periodicity of square numbers in the MID, the most effective approach is to see how the central pairs of complementary divisors of integers behave within the MID.

Figure 2. C001642 Depicts polygonal pathways representing central pairs of complementary divisors of integers within the MID.

The positive numbers are produced by the central pairs of complementary divisors:

$$(d_{c1}; d_{c2}) = (\text{https://oeis.org/A033676}; \text{https://oeis.org/A033677}) \\ = (-\text{https://oeis.org/A033677}; -\text{https://oeis.org/A033676})$$

The negative numbers are produced by the central pairs of complementary divisors:

$$(d_{c1}; d_{c2}) = (-\text{https://oeis.org/A033676}; \text{https://oeis.org/A033677}) \\ = (-\text{https://oeis.org/A033677}; \text{https://oeis.org/A033676})$$

Square numbers show a unique periodicity along the number line, forming distinct points on the x-axis. Interestingly, (square-1) numbers, being the predecessors of square numbers, share the same periodicity but are offset by a single unit along the number line.

This alignment yields a significant result: the points representing the central pairs of complementary divisors for both square numbers and their corresponding (square-1) predecessors combine to form an isosceles triangle, possessing an area of 1.

Figure 3. C001643 The yellow triangles with an area of 1 formed by the central pairs of complementary divisors for both square numbers and their respective (square-1) predecessors.

2.2 Divisors and Isosceles Triangles:

Analyzing the divisors of square and (square-1) numbers within the MID unveils consistent patterns. The central pair of complementary divisors for square numbers always keeps a difference of 0, signifying the inherent symmetry within these numbers. Conversely, for (square-1) numbers, the difference between their central pair of complementary divisors stays consistently 2.

This intriguing relationship between square and (square-1) numbers forms distinct isosceles triangles within the MID. These triangles, represented by square and (square-1) numbers and their corresponding divisors, consistently produce a base (b) of 2 units (reflecting the difference between the central pair of complementary divisors for (square-1) numbers) and a height (h) of 1-unit (representing the horizontal distance between square and (square-1) numbers). This configuration ensures that all formed isosceles triangles keep a constant area of 1 within the MID.

2.3 Repeated Patterns and Triangular Symmetry:

This triangular pattern, prominently seen between square and (square-1) numbers along with their divisors in the MID, shows perpetual repetition. It consistently generates isosceles triangles with an area of 1, emphasizing the uniformity and symmetry within the relationship.

3 Exploring the Interplay Between Square Numbers and Their Successors: A Triangular Perspective in MID

Examining the relationship between square numbers and their subsequent counterparts, specifically the (following (square-1)) numbers, unveils a repeated triangular pattern within the domain of integers in MID.

A novel approach lies in constructing a recurring triangle among all square numbers, denoted by y^2 , and their sequential counterparts represented as $(y + 1)^2 - 1$:

$$x = (y + 1)^2 - 1 = y^2 + 2y = y(y + 2) = h(h - 2)$$

This perspective offers insight into why all square numbers possess $b_{dm} = 0$ and all (square-1) numbers maintain $b_{dm} = 2$.

Every square number follows the form of $y^2 = y(y + 0)$. Consequently, $d_{c2} = d_{c1}$ and $b_{dm} = 0$ for any square number.

On the other hand, every (following (square-1)) number takes the form of $(y + 1)^2 - 1 = y(y + 2)$. Consequently, $d_{c2} = d_{c1} + 2$ and $b_{dm} = 2$ for any (square-1) number.

This recurrent pattern perpetuates indefinitely within the MID, creating innumerable triangles, each with a variable area given by $area = 2y$:

Figure 4. C001644 Illustrates the rectangle triangle, showcased in half-red, showcasing the variable area formation between the central pair of complementary divisors of square numbers $x = y^2$ and their (following (square-1)) counterparts $x = (y + 1)^2 - 1 = y(y + 2)$.

All these rectangle triangles consistently maintain a fixed side $s_1 = 2$ and another perpendicular side $s_2 = 2y$, fluctuating in accordance with the Y-coordinate of the central divisor of the square number.

The hypotenuse of this rectangle triangle is calculated as $h = \sqrt{y^2 + 4}$, encapsulating the triangular form.

The area of the rectangle triangle is computed as $area = \frac{2 \cdot 2y}{2} = 2y$, a fact supported by <https://oeis.org/A005843>.

These rectangle triangles stand distinct in the MID, devoid of any other divisors within, consistently upholding an area of $2y$.

3.1 Trapezoids produced by (Square-1) and Square Numbers

Exploring further, innumerable quadrilaterals can be created within the parabolic structure, delineating the space between all (square-1) and square numbers.

Thus, all divisors $d_1 \leq \sqrt{|x|}$ internal to the parabolas $x = \pm y^2$ belong to successive squares of area $(even)^2 = (2y)^2 = 4y^2$ <https://oeis.org/A016742>.

Figure 5. C001645 Illustrates squares of area $(2y)^2 = 4y^2$ in light-red outlining the smallest complementary divisors $d_1 \leq +\sqrt{|x|}$ represented by sequences arrays <https://oeis.org/A161906> or <https://oeis.org/A319135>.

3.2 The Square and the Successive Square

Many evident facets become clear within the MID.

Upon inspecting the MID displayed in Figure 5, starting from any square $x = y^2$, the addition of the longest side of the right-angled triangle $s_2 = 2y$ plus the height $h = 1$ of the isosceles triangle yields the subsequent square.

This observation stands out as $(y + 1)^2 = y^2 + 2y + 1 = y^2 + s_2 + h$. Consequently, it becomes apparent that for any given square of a number represented by y , its successor is consistently $y^2 + y + (y + 1)$.

For instance, if $y = 10$, then the square is $y^2 = 10^2 = 100$, and its successor is $10^2 + 10 + (10 + 1) = 10^2 + 10 + 11 = 11^2 = 121$.

3.3 The (Square Sequence Minus Square Number) Sequences

Expanding on the method of periodic localization from a square number to a (square-1) composite number, we recognize that all (square-1) numbers can be expressed in the form:

$$x = y^2 - 1 = (y + 1)(y - 1)$$

By defining $h = y - 1$, the expression $x = y^2 - 1 = (y + 1)(y - 1) = h(h + 2)$ emerges. Subsequently, by introducing $k = y + 1$, we achieve $x = y^2 - 1 = (y + 1)(y - 1) = h(h + 2) = k(k - 2)$.

Consequently, it can be concluded that all (square-1) numbers adhere to hyperbolic and quadratic formulations using $b_{dm} = 2$:

$$x \equiv n(n \pm 2) = n^2 \pm 2n$$

Generalizing, for all numbers in the format of (square1 - square2):

$$x = y^2 - s^2$$

$$x = y^2 - s^2 = (y + s)(y - s)$$

By defining $d_2 = y + s$ and $d_1 = y - s$, it is evident that $b_{dm} = d_2 - d_1 = 2s$.

Hence, all (square1-square2) numbers adhere to hyperbolic and quadratic formulations:

$$(\text{square1} - \text{square2}) \equiv y(y \pm 2s) = y^2 \pm (2s)y$$

$$(\text{square1} - \text{square2}) \equiv y(y \pm \text{even}) = y^2 \pm (\text{even})y$$

In this classification, the focus is not on the offset of the generated sequences. Rather, the significance lies in each quadratic sequence producing a class of integers in the same parabolic shape, or equivalently, having the same coefficient $a = 1$. The shape of a polynomial in quadratics is defined by the coefficient a via the method of finite differences.

For instance, considering $x = y^2 - 81$, where $s^2 = 81$, thus $s = \pm 9$, $2s = \pm 18$, we observe:

$$x = y^2 - 81 \equiv y(y + 18) = y^2 + 18y \equiv y(y - 18) = y^2 - 18y$$

$$y^2 - 81 \equiv y(y \pm 18)$$

The parabolic form $y^2 - 81$ is equivalent to the hyperbolic form $y(y \pm 18)$. While they generate the same integer sequence, they have different offsets. The formula $y(y + 18)$ has an offset $f = -9$, $y(y - 18)$ has an offset $f = +9$, and $y^2 - 81$ has an offset $f = 0$.

All these formulas generate the same sequence of the integers based on the same $b_d = 18$.

Utilizing offset study[12]:

1. Formula $x = y^2 - 81 = [-80, -81, -80]$ has offset $f = 0$. Prime -17 at indices $y = \pm 8$. Prime 19 at indices $y = \pm 10$.
2. Formula $x = y^2 + 18y = [-17, 0, 19]$ has offset $f = -9$. Prime -17 at indices $y = -1$ and $y = -17$. Prime 19 at indices $y = 1$ and $y = -19$.

3. Formula $x = y^2 - 18y = [19,0,-17]$ has offset $f = +9$. Prime -17 at indices $y = 1$ and $y = 17$. Prime 19 at indices $y = -1$ and $y = +19$.

All these formulas generate the same integer sequence with different offsets. All elements in the sequence are square numbers from the square sequence <https://oeis.org/A000290> minus the fixed square number $9^2 = 81$. Due to their hyperbolic form, these sequences are composite generators, leading to either zero or a finite number of primes.

This allows us to chart all parabolas encompassing all pair of complementary divisors in the form of (square sequence minus square number) or all numbers in the form of $b_d = 2s = \text{even}$, $x = y(y \pm 2s) = y^2 \pm (2s)y$:

Figure 6. C001646 The D-SUB parabolas, revealing all (square sequence-square number) numbers along the number line X-axis.

For instance, considering the two parabolas generating integers in the form of $x = -(square\ sequence) + 25 = -y^2 + 5^2$ at offset $f = 0$, they are represented by the equations $x = (-y^2 + 5 * 2y) = y(-y + 10)$ and $x = (-y^2 - 5 * 2y) = y(-y - 10)$. These parabolas encompass vertical divisors forming integers such as:

$$\begin{aligned}
25 &= 5 * 5 = -5 * -5, b_d = 0 \\
24 &= 4 * 6 = -4 * -6, b_d = 2 \\
21 &= 3 * 7 = -3 * -7, b_d = 4 \\
16 &= 2 * 8 = -2 * -8, b_d = 6
\end{aligned}$$

And so forth.

4 Exploring the Relationship Between Squares, Oblongs, and (Following (Square-1)) Numbers

In our prior work detailed in "The SOM Numbers" [7], we established an intrinsic connection between square numbers and oblong numbers. Demonstrating that whenever a property pertains to square numbers, a corresponding equivalent exists in the realm of oblong numbers, and vice versa.

All rectangle triangles share a unifying factor—an oblong number $x = y^2 + y$ positioned equidistantly between the square number $x = y^2$ and the subsequent (following (square-1)) number $x = (y + 1)^2 - 1 = y^2 + 2y$.

Remarkably, all oblong numbers have a consistent difference between their central pair of complementary divisors, denoted as $b_{dm} = 1$.

Moreover, if composites in the form of (square sequence-square number) exist, a parallel existence of composites in the form of (oblong sequence-oblong number) must follow.

4.1 The (Oblong Sequence Minus Oblong Number) Sequences

Let us delve into the properties of numbers expressed in the format of (oblong1-oblong2):

$$\begin{aligned}
x &= y(y \pm 1) - m(m \pm 1) \\
x &= (y^2 \pm y) - (m^2 \pm m) \\
x &= y^2 \pm y - m^2 \mp m \\
x &= (y^2 - m^2) \pm y \mp m \\
x &= (y^2 + m^2) \pm y + (-2m^2 \mp m) \\
x &= (y^2 - 2my + m^2) + (2my \pm y) + (-2m^2 \mp m) \\
x &= (y - m)^2 + (2m \pm 1)y - (2m \pm 1)m \\
x &= (y - m)^2 + (2m \pm 1)(y - m)
\end{aligned}$$

Let us substitute $n = y - m$:

$$\begin{aligned}
x &= n^2 + (2m \pm 1)n = n(n + (2m \pm 1)) \\
x &= n(n + odd) = n^2 + (odd)n
\end{aligned}$$

Since x is always even within this sequence, there is no occurrence of an odd prime element.

Figure 7. C001647 Illustrates the oblong and (oblong minus two) quadrilaterals in maroon, showcasing the positioning of oblong numbers along the X-axis, akin to the periodicity observed previously with square and (square-1) numbers.

Figure 8. C001648 Demonstrates the D-DES parabolas, highlighting the relationships between (oblong1-oblong2) pairs, providing insights into the periodicity and distribution of oblong numbers.

5 Encompassing All Integers with (Square Minus Square) and (Oblong Minus Oblong) Numbers

We can establish the following conclusions:

1. All CGs (Composite Generators) in the format of (square1-square2) exhibit $b_m = \text{even}$. They adhere to the structure:

$$x = y(y \pm 2m) = y^2 \pm (2m)y = y^2 \pm (\text{even})y$$

2. All CGs in the format of (oblong1-oblong2) exhibit $b_m = \text{odd}$. They follow the pattern:

$$x = y(y \pm (2m - 1)) = y^2 \pm (2m - 1)y = y^2 \pm (\text{odd})y$$

3. We can express all integers $x = d_1 * d_2$ in function of the smallest difference between the two divisors of the central pair of complementary divisors:

$$x = d_1 * d_2 = y(y \pm b_m) = y^2 \pm b_m y$$

Hence, the SUB-parabolas in the form of $x = y(y \pm 2m) = y^2 \pm (2m)y$ cover all integers with $b_m = \text{even} = 2m$, where two distinct (square1 minus square2) numbers can invariably yield the integer $x = d_1 * d_2 = y(y \pm 2m) = y^2 \pm (2m)y = y^2 \pm (\text{even})y$.

Similarly, DES-parabolas in the form of $x = y(y \pm (2m - 1)) = y^2 \pm (2m - 1)y$ encompass all integers with $b_m = \text{odd} = 2m - 1$. These DES-parabolas feature two unique (oblong1 minus oblong2) numbers, their difference resulting in the integer $x = y(y \pm (2m - 1)) = y^2 \pm (2m - 1)y = y^2 \pm (\text{odd})y$.

5.1 The Sum and Product of the Roots of Quadratic Formulas

The roots of $x = ay^2 + by + c$ are

$$y_1 = \frac{-b + \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a}$$

$$y_2 = \frac{-b - \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a}$$

Therefore:

$$y_1 + y_2 = -\frac{b}{a}$$

$$y_1 * y_2 = \frac{c}{a}$$

Consequently:

$$\frac{x}{a} = y^2 + \frac{b}{a}y + \frac{c}{a}$$

$$\frac{x}{a} = y^2 - (y_1 + y_2)y + y_1 * y_2$$

5.2 The Parabolic $x = y(y - b)$ Numbers Over the X-axis

When $a = -1$ and $c = 0$, the quadratic equation becomes:

$$x = -y^2 + by = y(-y + b)$$

Setting them as all products $x = d_1 * d_2$, we have:

$$d_1 = y$$

$$d_2 = -y + b$$

Resulting in:

$$d_1 + d_2 = b$$

Thus:

$$x = -y^2 + by = y(-y + b) = d_1 * d_2 = -y^2 + (d_1 + d_2)y$$

This allow every integer x to be represented both in the hyperbolic form $x = d_1 * d_2$ and in the parabolic form $x = -y^2 + (d_1 + d_2)y$, where $d_2 + d_1 = b_s$ and b_d is the difference between the pair of complementary divisors $(d_1; d_2)$ of the integer $x = d_1 * d_2$.

5.3 Illustrative Examples:

Figure 9. [C000671](#) Parabolic sequences $x = -y^2 + by$ for $6 \leq b \leq 9$.

b = 6:

Displayed in green is the D-SUB parabola $x = -y^2 + 6y = y(-y + 6)$.

The symmetry point's Y-coordinate is $y_{sp} = -\frac{b}{2a} = -\frac{6}{2(-1)} = +3$.

The Y-coordinate produces an offset $f = \text{roundz}\left[-\frac{b}{2a}\right] = \text{roundz}[+3] = 3$.

$x = -y^2 + 6y$ at offset $f = 0$ yields $x = -y^2 + 9 = -\text{square sequence} + \text{square}[3]$.

Spanning from $-\infty < y < \infty$ the sequence showcases:

$$\{\dots, -72, -55, -40, -27, -16, -7, 0, 5, 8, 9, 8, 5, 0, -7, -16, -27, -40, -55, -72, \dots\}$$

It is a CG sequence featuring two primes: 5 and -7.

This sequence is listed in the OEIS as <https://oeis.org/A028560>.

SUB-type D-Parabola $x = -y^2 + 6y = y(-y+6) \equiv -y^2 + 9$											
Description	Equation	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
decreasing divisor	$d_1 \leq \sqrt{ x }$	3	2	1	0	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6
increasing divisor	$d_2 \geq \sqrt{ x }$	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
dif pcd	$b_d = d_2 - d_1$	0	2	4	6	8	10	12	14	16	18
sum pcd	$b_s = d_1 + d_2$	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
symmetry point	$y_{sp} = b_s / 2 = (d_1 + d_2) / 2$	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
sequence data	$x = d_1 * d_2$	9	8	5	0	-7	-16	-27	-40	-55	-72
method of diff.	dif		1	3	5	7	9	11	13	15	17
coefficient 2a	difdif			-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2
parabola proof	difdifdif				0	0	0	0	0	0	0
square root x	$\sqrt{ x }$	3	2.828	2.236	0	2.646	4	5.196	6.325	7.416	8.485

Figure 10. The CG SUB-type D-parabola $x = -y^2 + 6y$.

b = 7:

Displayed in violet is the D-DES parabola $x = -y^2 + 7y = y(-y + 7)$.

The symmetry point's Y-coordinate is $y_{sp} = -\frac{b}{2a} = -\frac{7}{2(-1)} = +3.5$.

The Y-coordinate produces an offset $f = \text{roundz}\left[-\frac{b}{2a}\right] = \text{roundz}[+3.5] = 3$.

$x = -y^2 + 7y$ at offset $f = 0$ yields $x = -y^2 + y + 12 = -\text{oblong sequence} + \text{oblong}[4]$.

Spanning from $-\infty < y < \infty$ the sequence showcases:

{..., -60, -44, -30, -18, -8, 0, 6, 10, 12, 12, 10, 6, 0, -8, -18, -30, -44, -60, -78, ...}

It is a CG sequence devoid of primes.

This sequence is listed in the OEIS as <https://oeis.org/A028563>.

DES-type D-Parabola $x = -y^2 + 7y = y(-y + 7) \equiv -y^2 + y + 12$											
Description	Equation	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
decreasing divisor	$d_1 \leq \sqrt{ x }$	3	2	1	0	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6
increasing divisor	$d_2 \geq \sqrt{ x }$	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
dif pcd	$b_d = d_2 - d_1$	1	3	5	7	9	11	13	15	17	19
sum pcd	$b_s = d_1 + d_2$	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7
symmetry point	$y_{sp} = b_s / 2 = (d_1 + d_2) / 2$	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.5
sequence data	$x = d_1 * d_2$	12	10	6	0	-8	-18	-30	-44	-60	-78
method of diff.	dif		2	4	6	8	10	12	14	16	18
coefficient 2a	difdif			-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2
parabola proof	difdifdif				0	0	0	0	0	0	0
square root $\sqrt{ x }$	$\sqrt{ x }$	3.464	3.162	2.449	0	2.828	4.243	5.477	6.633	7.746	8.832

Figure 11. The CG DES-type D-parabola $x = -y^2 + 7y$.

b = 8:

Displayed in pink is the D-SUB parabola $x = -y^2 + 8y = y(-y + 8)$.

The symmetry point's Y-coordinate is $y_{sp} = -\frac{b}{2a} = -\frac{8}{2(-1)} = +4$.

The Y-coordinate produces an offset $f = \text{roundz}\left[-\frac{b}{2a}\right] = \text{roundz}[+4] = 4$.

$x = -y^2 + 8y$ at offset $f = 0$ yields $x = -y^2 + 16 = -\text{square sequence} + \text{square}[4]$.

Spanning from $-\infty < y < \infty$ the sequence showcases:

{..., -65, -48, -33, -20, -9, 0, 7, 12, 15, 16, 15, 12, 7, 0, -9, -20, -33, -48, -65, ...}

It is a CG sequence featuring the prime 7.

This sequence is listed in the OEIS as <https://oeis.org/A028566>.

SUB-type D-Parabola $x=-y^2+8y=y(-y+8)\equiv -y^2+16$											
Description	Equation	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
decreasing divisor	$d_1<=\sqrt{ x }$	4	3	2	1	0	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5
increasing divisor	$d_2>=\sqrt{ x }$	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
dif pcd	$b_d=d_2-d_1$	0	2	4	6	8	10	12	14	16	18
sum pcd	$b_s=d_1+d_2$	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
symmetry point	$y_{sp}=b_s/2=(d_1+d_2)/2$	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
sequence data	$x=d_1*d_2$	16	15	12	7	0	-9	-20	-33	-48	-65
method of diff.	dif		1	3	5	7	9	11	13	15	17
coefficient 2a	difdif			-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2
parabola proof	difdifdif				0	0	0	0	0	0	0
square root $ x $	$\sqrt{ x }$	4	3.873	3.464	2.646	0	3	4.472	5.745	6.928	8.062

Figure 12. The CG SUB-type D-parabola $x = -y^2 + 8y$.

b = 9:

Displayed in violet is the D-DES parabola $x = -y^2 + 9y = y(-y + 9)$.

The symmetry point's Y-coordinate is $y_{sp} = -\frac{b}{2a} = -\frac{9}{2(-1)} = +4.5.5$.

The Y-coordinate produces an offset $f = \text{roundz}\left[-\frac{b}{2a}\right] = \text{roundz}[+4.5] = 4$.

$x = -y^2 + 9y$ at offset $f = 0$ yields $x = -y^2 + y + 20 = -\text{oblong sequence} + \text{oblong}[5]$.

Spanning from $-\infty < y < \infty$ the sequence showcases:

$\{\dots, -52, -36, -22, -10, 0, 8, 14, 18, 20, 20, 18, 14, 8, 0, -10, -22, -36, -52, -70, \dots\}$

It is a CG sequence devoid of primes.

This sequence is listed in the OEIS as <https://oeis.org/A028569>.

DES-type D-Parabola $x=-y^2+9y=y(-y+9)\equiv -y^2+y+20$											
Description	Equation	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
decreasing divisor	$d_1<=\sqrt{ x }$	4	3	2	1	0	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5
increasing divisor	$d_2>=\sqrt{ x }$	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
dif pcd	$b_d=d_2-d_1$	1	3	5	7	9	11	13	15	17	19
sum pcd	$b_s=d_1+d_2$	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9
symmetry point	$y_{sp}=b_s/2=(d_1+d_2)/2$	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5
sequence data	$x=d_1*d_2$	20	18	14	8	0	-10	-22	-36	-52	-70
method of diff.	dif		2	4	6	8	10	12	14	16	18
coefficient 2a	difdif			-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2
parabola proof	difdifdif				0	0	0	0	0	0	0
square root $ x $	$\sqrt{ x }$	4.472	4.243	3.742	2.828	0	3.162	4.69	6	7.211	8.367

Figure 13. The CG DES-type D-parabola $x = -y^2 + 9y$.

With this combination of one complementary divisor being decreasing (d_1) and the other increasing (d_2), always starting from all pairs of complementary divisors, results in all the possible product combinations that we can have, equal to all combinations we have in hyperbolic MT[13].

All sequences formed from the tables above, always start either from an oblong number or a square number. Then it is possible to cover all MID's divisors with the D-parabolas with coefficient $a = -1$:

5.4 Combining Complementary Divisors in Parabolic Sequences:

By pairing one increasing complementary divisor (d_2) with a decreasing one (d_1), consistently deriving from all pairs of complementary divisors, we obtain a comprehensive range of potential product combinations, effectively mirroring all the combinations found in hyperbolic MT[13].

5.5 Sequencing Characteristics:

All sequences derived from the tables start (closest to the symmetry point) from either an oblong number or a square number. Consequently, it becomes feasible to encompass all MID's divisors utilizing the D-parabolas with offset $f \neq 0$ with 2nd degree coefficient of $a = -1$:

Figure 14. C001649 The SUB-type and DES-type D-parabolas covering MID.

5.6 Invitation for Exploration:

The exploration of C-parabolas is left to the reader's discretion. In Figure 15, an informative table depicts the equivalence of the first 32 sequences found in the OEIS. This table comprises a column dedicated to hyperbolic formulas and two columns containing parabolic formulas. One of the parabolic formula columns exhibits a non-zero offset, while the other denotes an offset of zero.

b_{dm}	OEIS	Name	CG offset $f \geq 0$	CG offset $f = 0$	
0	https://oeis.org/A000290	square-0	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 0)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 0y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - 0$
1	https://oeis.org/A002378	oblong-0	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 1)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 1y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 0$
2	https://oeis.org/A005563	square-1	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 2)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 2y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - 1$
3	https://oeis.org/A028552	oblong-2	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 3)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 3y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 2$
4	https://oeis.org/A028347	square-4	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 4)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 4y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - 4$
5	https://oeis.org/A028557	oblong-6	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 5)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 5y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 6$
6	https://oeis.org/A028560	square-9	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 6)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 6y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - 9$
7	https://oeis.org/A028563	oblong-12	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 7)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 7y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 12$
8	https://oeis.org/A028566	square-16	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 8)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 8y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - 16$
9	https://oeis.org/A028569	oblong-20	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 9)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 9y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 20$
10	https://oeis.org/A098603	square-25	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 10)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 10y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - 25$
11	https://oeis.org/A119412	oblong-30	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 11)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 11y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 30$
12	https://oeis.org/A098847	square-36	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 12)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 12y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - 36$
13	https://oeis.org/A132759	oblong-42	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 13)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 13y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 42$
14	https://oeis.org/A098848	square-49	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 14)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 14y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - 49$
15	https://oeis.org/A132760	oblong-56	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 15)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 15y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 56$
16	https://oeis.org/A098849	square-64	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 16)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 16y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - 64$
17	https://oeis.org/A132761	oblong-72	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 17)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 17y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 72$
18	https://oeis.org/A098850	square-81	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 18)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 18y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - 81$
19	https://oeis.org/A132762	oblong-90	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 19)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 19y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 90$
20	https://oeis.org/A120071	square-100	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 20)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 20y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - 100$
21	https://oeis.org/A132763	oblong-110	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 21)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 21y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 110$
22	https://oeis.org/A132764	square-121	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 22)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 22y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - 121$
23	https://oeis.org/A132765	oblong-132	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 23)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 23y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 132$
24	https://oeis.org/A132766	square-144	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 24)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 24y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - 144$
25	https://oeis.org/A132767	oblong-156	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 25)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 25y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 156$
26	https://oeis.org/A132768	square-169	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 26)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 26y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - 169$
27	https://oeis.org/A132769	oblong-182	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 27)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 27y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 182$
28	https://oeis.org/A132770	square-196	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 28)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 28y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - 196$
29	https://oeis.org/A132771	oblong-210	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 29)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 29y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 210$
30	https://oeis.org/A132772	square-225	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 30)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 30y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - 225$
31	https://oeis.org/A132773	oblong-240	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 31)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 31y$	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 240$

Figure 15. Table of quadratic CGs with coefficient $a = 1$ that cover all elements of the FMT and MID. They are the diagonals in FMT with a slope of 1: 1 (45°) and parabolas with coefficient $a = \pm 1$ in the MID.

The author first encountered this theory in May 2017. Several figures were subsequently published, including:

Figure 16. One of the first illustrations depicting parabolic patterns within the MID on May 20, 2017. [Link to the figure: <https://www.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=782309838604429&set=pb.100004762603623.-2207520000>].

6 The SOM zones

The MID (Map of Integers and their Divisors) can be divided into unlimited zones, each bounded by vertical lines following the formulas $x = \text{square}$, $x = \text{oblong}$, and $x = \text{square} - 1$. This division is visually demonstrated in the figure below:

Figure 17. C001652: Representation of the SO, OM, and MS Zones in the MID.

This figure illustrates the intricate arrangement of the SO (Square to Oblong), OM (Oblong to Square Minus 1), and MS (Square Minus 1 to Square) zones on the positive side of the number line over the X-axis in the MID. It presents a detailed graphical representation, highlighting the complex relationships between integers and their divisors through color-coded lines:

- Yellow Lines: These lines, representing $x = \text{square number}$, effectively delineate the boundaries of square numbers. They provide a clear visual demarcation of these numerical values and their divisors within the MID.
- Red-Dark Lines: Corresponding to $x = \text{oblong numbers}$, these lines cover the oblong numbers and their divisors.
- Orange-Dark Lines: Representing $x = (\text{square minus } 1)$ numbers, these lines map out the area where each number is one less than a perfect square.

Each zone is numerically matched to a corresponding integer y coordinate, as defined by the red parabola $x = y^2$. Each zone exists for each integer coordinate y and vice versa. Sequentially,

there are always three zones SO, OM, and MS for each integer value of y , as will be further explored in the following sections.

The visualization in Figure 17 serves as an invaluable tool for comprehending the spatial and numerical relationships between different zones in the MID, offering a clear, color-coordinated approach to understanding these mathematical concepts.

6.1 The SO Zone in MID

The MID (Map of Integers and Divisors) is a graphical representation mapping the relationship between integers and their divisors. Within this map, the SO (Square to Oblong) Zone is a prominent feature, encompassing innumerable distinct regions. Each SO region is defined for a specific value of y and is delineated by two lines:

1. **Initial Line (Square Number Line):** For a given y this line is described by the equation $x = y^2$ and covers all positive and negative divisors of the square number. It establishes the initial boundary of the SO region.
2. **Final Line (Oblong Number Line):** The other boundary of the SO region is established by the line $x = y^2 + y$, which passes through all positive and negative divisors of the oblong number.

The area between these two lines, for each value of y , constitutes an individual SO region in the MID. Within each of these regions, when focusing on the divisors of integer x that are less than or equal to y , a specific square is formed. The vertices of this square in the first quadrant (Q1) are:

- $V_1 = (y^2, 0)$
- $V_2 = (y^2, y)$
- $V_3 = (y^2 + y, y)$
- $V_4 = (y^2 + y, 0)$

This square in first quadrant (Q1) covers all the smallest complementary divisors $1 \leq d_1 \leq y$ of all x integers within $y^2 \leq x \leq y^2 + y$. These are the divisors within the red parabolic curve, defined by the equation $x = y^2$. Outside the square (outside the parabola) lie the largest complementary divisors $x \geq d_2 \geq y$ of the same integers, produced by the X-axis.

Thus, the MID presents an infinite series of SO regions, each with its unique characteristic and a square defined by the aforementioned vertices, illustrating the rich and complex structure of integers and their divisors.

6.2 The OM Zone in MID

Within the MID, the OM (Oblong to Square Minus 1) Zone is a notable feature, comprising innumerable distinct regions. Each OM region is defined for a specific value of y and is delimited by two lines:

1. **Initial Line (Oblong Number Line):** Passes through all positive and negative divisors of the divisors of the oblong number, represented by the equation $x = y^2 + y$.

2. Final Line (Square Minus 1 Number Line): Passes through all positive and negative divisors of the (square minus 1) number, given by $x = y^2 + 2y$.

The space between these lines, for each value of y , forms an individual OM region in the MID. Within each region, focusing on the divisors of integers x that are less than or equal to y , a specific square is formed. The vertices of this square in the first quadrant are:

- $V_1 = (y^2 + y, 0)$
- $V_2 = (y^2 + y, y)$
- $V_3 = (y^2 + 2y, y)$
- $V_4 = (y^2 + 2y, 0)$

Similarly, the same phenomenon is observed in this instance. Within the boundaries of the square, it encompasses all the smallest complementary divisors $1 \leq d_1 \leq y$ of all integers x that fall in the range $y^2 + y \leq x \leq y^2 + 2y$. Conversely, outside the square are located the largest complementary divisor $x \geq d_2 \geq y$ of the same integers, produced by the X-axis.

Consequently, the MID displays an infinite series of OM regions, each with its unique characteristic and a square in quadrant 1 (Q1) defined by the mentioned vertices, demonstrating the intricate and complex structure of integers and their divisors.

It is particularly noteworthy that the square within the OM Zone possesses the same area as the square in the SO (Square to Oblong) Zone, emphasizing a fascinating symmetry and proportionality within the MID. Despite corresponding to different numerical ranges and divisor relationships, these squares share an equal area, highlighting a harmonious and balanced mathematical structure within the MID.

6.3 The MS Zone in MID

The MID, as a graphical representation, maps the relationship between integers and their divisors. The MS (Square Minus 1 to Square) Zone within this map encompasses a multitude of distinct regions. Each MS region is defined for a specific value of y and is bounded by two lines:

- 1. Initial Line (Square Minus 1 Number Line):** Passes through all positive and negative divisors of the divisors of (square minus 1) number, given by $x = y^2 + 2y$.
- 2. Final Line (Next Square Number Line):** This line is described by the equation $x = (y + 1)^2$, covering all positive and negative divisors of the next square number. It defines the final border of the MS region.

The space between these lines, for each value of y and $y + 1$, forms an individual MS region in the MID. Within each of these regions, focusing on the divisors of integers x that are less than or equal to $y + 1$, a specific trapezoid is formed. The vertices of this trapezoid in the first quadrant are:

- $V_1 = (y^2 + 2y, 0)$
- $V_2 = (y^2 + 2y, y)$
- $V_3 = (y^2 + 2y + 1, y)$
- $V_4 = (y^2 + 2y + 1, 0)$

Within this trapezoid are covered all the smallest complementary divisors $1 \leq d_1 \leq y$ of only two integers: the square minus 1 number $x = y^2 + 2y$ and the next square number given by $x = y^2 + 2y + 1$.

Hence, the MID exhibits an infinite series of MS regions, each distinguished by its unique characteristic and a trapezoid in first the quadrant (Q1) defined by the specified vertices.

6.4 Conclusion on the SOM Zones

Just as the entirety of the divisors in the MID exhibits a complete symmetry in their distribution across the four quadrants of the XY plane, centered uniquely at the origin point (0,0), each SOM zone, composed of SO, OM, and MS zones, seeks to replicate this symmetry. However, in the case of the SOM zones, the center of symmetry shifts to each oblong number along the X-axis. This design mirrors the overarching symmetry of the MID, adapting it to the localized context of each SOM zone. By positioning the oblong number as the new center, these zones not only maintain the inherent balance and harmony of the MID's structure but also highlight the nuanced shifts in divisor relationships and numerical patterns as we move across different values along the X-axis. This approach underscores the meticulous attention to symmetry and balance that is a hallmark of the MID's intricate mathematical framework.

7 The SOM Zones Lines Outside the Parabola

In the context of the MID (Map of Integers and their Divisors), the SOM zones not only interact with specific lines outside the parabola $x = y^2$ but also have a key relationship with divisors. The lines in question effectively cover all divisors that are the largest complementary divisor d_2 for each integer x where $d_2 \geq \sqrt{x}$.

This characteristic becomes evident when we explore the reason why these lines traverse the SOM zones:

- Within each SOM zone, bounded by the verticals of consecutive squares (e.g., $x = 4^2 = 16$ and $x = 5^2 = 25$ for the 4th SOM zone), the lines $x = ny$ encompass all largest complementary divisors d_2 of the integers in that range. These divisors d_2 satisfy the condition $d_2 \geq \sqrt{x}$.
- Consequently, the integers within each SOM zone are linked to a specific set of complementary divisors, determined by the count of lines passing above the zone. For instance, in the 4th SOM zone, all integers from 16 to 24 are covered by lines $x=ny$ for $1 \leq n \leq 4$, indicating that each integer can have up to 4 pairs of such largest complementary divisors.

This pattern, observed consistently across the SOM zones in the MID, illustrates the extensive coverage of divisors, with particular emphasis on the largest complementary divisors. These zones serve as a vivid demonstration of the MID's intricate mathematical structure. They reveal how each zone, along with its associated lines, comprehensively maps out the divisor

relationships, delving into the nuances of the complementary pairs of divisors for each integer. This detailed representation not only provides a visual interpretation of these mathematical relationships but also underscores the complexity and interconnectivity inherent within the MID's framework.

Figure 18. C001653 Representation of the SO, OM and MS Zones in MID showing the Largest Divisors Lines Outside Parabola.

The lines start at central divisors of the squares.

8 First Reasoning: The Prime Number Distribution

When we map the distribution of central divisors $\pm$ (<https://oeis.org/A033676> and <https://oeis.org/A033677>) in the MID (Map of Integers and Divisors) using polyline techniques, and simultaneously highlight the SO and OM zones as squares situated within the parabola, we obtain a figure that vividly illustrates this relationship. This graphical representation not only demonstrates the location and distribution of central divisors but also clearly reveals the

geometric structure of the SOM zones framed within the parabolic contour. This arrangement provides a profound and intuitive visual understanding of the interconnection between composite and prime numbers, each with their divisors, in the context of the MID.

Figure 19. C001654 The distribution of the central divisors in the MID with polylines over the SOM zones.

Whatever the pair of consecutive SO and OM zones squares, they will always obey the following rules:

Figure 20. C001655: Figure Illustrating a Standard Distribution of Trivial and Central Divisors in a Generic SOM Zone.

Each square of area n^2 has $n + 1$ horizontal (This is because the first horizontal row in any square zone is the X-axis ($y = 0$ row)). Similarly, each square has $n + 1$ vertical lines. This means every square of zone SO or OS has the same number of ($n + 1$) horizontal and vertical Cartesian lines.

The divisors $d_1 \leq \sqrt{|x|} \leq y$ can only be at the intersections of these horizontal Cartesian lines with the vertical Cartesian lines that belong to its square.

The number of Cartesian points within each square of area n^2 covered by $d_1 \leq \sqrt{|x|}$ divisors are the oblong number $n(n + 1)$. This is because the first horizontal row in any square zone is the X-axis ($y = 0$ row) which do not have any divisor. The X-axis is not a location for the distribution of the $d_1 \leq \sqrt{|x|}$ divisors. The X-axis is the place of the product of each pair of complementary divisors.

The first horizontal row above X-axis is the row of smallest trivial divisors $d_{t1} = 1$ at $y = 1$. They are consecutively uniform overall vertical columns of the square. They are complementary divisors to the largest trivial divisors $d_{t2} = x > \sqrt{|x|}$. All the largest trivial d_{t2} divisors in MID are over the diagonal $x = y$ with the inclination of 1: 1.

The highest horizontal row ($y = n$ row) is the row of the 3 central divisors $d_{c1} = y = n$. They are equidistant distributed over the two possible vertical columns edges of each square:

- In zone SO: divisors are distributed in and between vertical edge columns $x = n^2 = n(n + 0)$ (square) and $x = n^2 + n = n(n + 1)$ (oblong).
- In zone OM: similarly, between vertical edge columns $x = n^2 + n = n(n + 1)$ (oblong) and $x = n^2 + 2n = n(n + 2)$ (square-1).

The 3 central divisors $d_{c1} = n$ are complementary to the 3 central divisors $d_{c2} \geq \sqrt{|x|}$ with values (1) $d_{c2} = d_{c1} = n$, (2) $d_{c2} = n + 1$, and (3) $d_{c2} = n + 2$. All the 3 central divisors d_{c2} are equidistantly over the diagonal $x = ny$ with inclination 1: n .

Now, when we analyze where to place the other central divisors $d_{c1} \leq \sqrt{|x|}$ of the integers between a square and an oblong or between an oblong and a square-1, the following situation common to all of them appears:

- Whatever the square is, we need to fill $(n - 1)$ vertical columns with central divisors $1 < d_{c1} \leq \sqrt{|x|}$.
- On the other hand, since we already used the horizontal rows 0, 1, and n , we can only use $(n - 2)$ values of $1 < d_{c1} < \sqrt{|x|}$.

Thus, since there will always be at least one column missing with $1 < d_{c1} \leq \sqrt{|x|}$, then certainly one of the columns will remain $d_{c1} = d_{t1} = 1$.

This proves that there is always at least one prime number between a square number and the following oblong number, and at least another distinct prime number between an oblong number and the following square number.

This proves the veracity of the comments in the sequences:

- <https://oeis.org/A307508> primes that are between a square number and its following oblong number.
- <https://oeis.org/A334163> primes that are between an oblong number and its following square number.

8.1 Alternative Analysis of Prime Number Distribution

A different approach to examining the distribution of prime numbers along the number line involves analyzing the divisors $d_2 \geq \sqrt{|x|}$.

As previously established, for each square with an area of n^2 , there are n blue diagonals with slopes ranging from 1:1 to 1: n . Notably, since the two edge columns of any square share the same 1: n diagonal to generate their central divisors $x \geq d_{c2} \geq \sqrt{|x|}$, only $(n - 1)$ diagonals remain to generate the d_{c2} for the other $(n - 1)$ columns. Consequently, in at least one column, the 1:1 diagonal will generate the central divisor that is trivially $d_{c2} = x = \text{prime} = d_{t2}$, which is complementary to $d_{c1} = d_{t1} = 1$.

These rectangular triangles with sides of $2y$ encompass all rows of the smallest complementary divisors $d_1 \leq \sqrt{x}$, situated inside the red zone of the parabola $x = y^2$. These always begin as:

- (1) the two central divisors of a square number $y^2 = y(y + 0)$,
- (2) then the lowest central divisor of an oblong number $y^2 + y = y(y + 1)$,
- (3) and lastly the lowest central divisor of the subsequent (square-1) number $y^2 + 2y = y(y + 2)$.

Every smallest complementary divisor $d_1 \leq \sqrt{x}$ always starts as one of the central divisors of a square number, then becomes the smallest central divisor of the following oblong number, and ultimately, the smallest central divisor of the subsequent (square-1) number.

In each SOM zone, these smallest central complementary divisors $d_1 = d_{c1} \leq \sqrt{x}$ have the same value and are separated by a distance equal to $d_1 = d_{c1} \leq \sqrt{x}$. Therefore, although d_1 periodically becomes a divisor of countless other integers, it only reemerges as the smallest central divisor in a similar irregular manner to the appearance of prime numbers along the number line. This irregularity reflects the complex and nuanced nature of prime number distribution within the MID framework.

9 Another Reasoning About Prime Number Distribution

An alternative approach to understanding the distribution of prime numbers on the numerical line is to acknowledge that numbers 1, 2, and 3 are primes, and that every positive integer can be expressed as the product of two complementary divisors, $x = d_1 * d_2$.

From this viewpoint, for any positive number $x > 3$, the expressions $x \pm d_1 = d_1 * (d_2 \pm 1)$ or $x \pm d_2 = d_2 * (d_1 \pm 1)$, will produce composite numbers. This means that any positive integer greater than 3, when added to or subtracted from its divisors greater than 1, invariably yields a composite number.

This perspective leads us to the possibility of conceiving various "sieves" for prime numbers within the context of the MID (Map of Integers and Divisors), which will be explored in the following sections.

10 Analyzing the Distribution of Composite Numbers

A relatively straightforward way to consider the impossibility of all composite numbers covering the integers on the number line is to expand the idea of adding or subtracting each divisor from the original number.

Let's begin our exploration with square numbers. Observe that $s^2 + k = (k + 1) \left(\frac{s^2 + k}{k + 1} \right)$. We'll limit this to $0 \leq k \leq s$. Now, all we need to do is prove that it's impossible for the term $\left(\frac{s^2 + k}{k + 1} \right)$ to always be an integer for all integer values of k .

10.1 On the Integer Solutions of the Expression $\left(\frac{s^2 + k}{k + 1} \right)$

We'll examine the claim that the expression $\left(\frac{s^2 + k}{k + 1} \right)$, where s^2 is a square number and k is an integer such that $0 < k < s$, yields an integer for every integer k in the interval from 1 to s .

Let's break down the expression:

1. Square Number s^2 : For a given s , s^2 is always an integer because it's the square of an integer.
2. Integer k : The variable k is an integer such that $0 < k < s$.
3. Expression Analysis: The expression is $\left(\frac{s^2 + k}{k + 1} \right)$. We need to show whether this expression is always an integer for every integer k in the given interval.

The claim is that this expression results in an integer for every integer k from 1 to s . However, this is not always true. Let's consider why:

- The numerator $s^2 + k$ is the sum of a square number and an integer, which is indeed an integer.
- The denominator $k + 1$ is also an integer.
- For the entire expression to be an integer, $s^2 + k$ must be divisible by $k + 1$ without any remainder.

However, there's no general rule or property that guarantees $s^2 + k$ is divisible by $k + 1$ for every integer k in the range $0 < k < s$. The divisibility depends on specific values of s and k , and it's not universally applicable for all integers within the range.

So, the claim does not hold for every integer k in the interval from 1 to s .

In conclusion, the expression $\left(\frac{s^2 + k}{k + 1} \right)$ can yield an integer for some specific values of k within the range, but it is not universally true for every integer in that interval. The result depends on the specific values of s and k .

10.2 On the Integer Solutions of the Expression $\left(\frac{s^2+s+k}{k+1}\right)$

Upon simplifying the expression $\left(\frac{s^2+s+k}{k+1}\right)$, it remains in the same form, $\left(\frac{k+s^2+s}{k+1}\right)$. Now, let's evaluate whether this expression yields an integer for every integer k in the interval from 1 to $s - 1$.

1. Numerator Analysis: The numerator $s^2 + s + k$ is an integer since it's a combination of integer operations on s and k .
2. Denominator Analysis: The denominator $k + 1$ is also an integer.
3. Expression as an Integer: For the entire expression to be an integer, the numerator must be divisible by the denominator without leaving any remainder.

Let's explore the divisibility:

- The numerator can be rewritten as $s(s + 1) + k$.
- Since s is an integer, $s(s + 1)$ is always an integer as it's the product of two consecutive integers (which is always even).
- Adding k to an even integer $s(s + 1)$ results in an integer.

However, whether this sum is divisible by $k + 1$ depends on the specific values of s and k . There's no general mathematical rule ensuring that $s(s + 1) + k$ is divisible by $k + 1$ for every integer k in the range from 1 to $s + 1$.

Therefore, the expression $\left(\frac{s^2+s+k}{k+1}\right)$ does not universally yield an integer for every integer k in the range from 1 to $s - 1$. The result depends on the specific values of s and k .

10.3 On the Integer Solutions of the Expressions from $\left(\frac{s^2+k}{k+1}\right)$ to $\left(\frac{s^2+s+k}{k+1}\right)$

Let's analyze the expressions $\left(\frac{s^2+k}{k+1}\right)$ and $\left(\frac{s^2+s+k}{k+1}\right)$ to determine if it's possible for all divisions by $k + 1$ to yield integers for all integer values of k in the interval $0 < k < s$. Furthermore, we want to verify if this applies to all numbers between s^2 and $s^2 + s$.

1. For $\left(\frac{s^2+k}{k+1}\right)$ to be an integer for all k in the specified interval, $s^2 + k$ must be divisible by $k + 1$ for each k .

2. Similarly, for $\left(\frac{s^2+s+k}{k+1}\right)$ to be an integer, $s^2 + s + k$ must be divisible by $k + 1$ for each k .

3. Additionally, we want all numbers between s^2 and $s^2 + s$ to also be divisible by $k + 1$ for each k in the interval.

Let's consider a counterexample to show that this is not possible:

If we take $k = s$, the first expression becomes $\left(\frac{s^2+s}{s+1}\right)$, and the second expression becomes $\left(\frac{s^2+2s}{s+1}\right)$. The first expression simplifies to s , which is an integer, but the second expression does not necessarily simplify to an integer. Moreover, not all numbers between s^2 and $s^2 + s$ will be divisible by $s + 1$.

Consider the number $s^2 + 1$. For $s^2 + 1$ to be divisible by $s + 1$, $s^2 + 1$ would have to be a multiple of $s + 1$, which rarely happens (only when $s = 0$).

Therefore, it is impossible for all expressions $\left(\frac{s^2+k}{k+1}\right)$, $\left(\frac{s^2+s+k}{k+1}\right)$, and all numbers between s^2 and $s^2 + s$ to be divisible by $k + 1$ for all integers k in the range $0 < k < s$. There will always be at least one number that is not an integer.

11 C001650 SPM6: A Geometric Sieve of Prime Numbers in the MID Based on Multiples of 6

The SPM6 (Sieve of Prime Numbers in the MID Based on Multiples of 6) offers a novel approach within the Map of Integers and Divisors (MID) framework for isolating prime numbers across the number line. This method employs a unique geometric configuration, drawing circles centered on multiples of 6, each with a radius equal to a prime number greater than 1.

SPM6 effectively visualizes and predicts the distribution of prime numbers. The SPM6 sieve introduces a novel method to investigate these enigmatic numbers through a geometric lens within the MID framework.

Methodology:

Circle Centering: Circles are centered on multiples of 6, acknowledging the property that prime numbers greater than 3 are always adjacent to a multiple of 6.

Radius Selection: The radius of each circle is set to a prime number that also serves as a divisor of a multiple of 6, creating a dynamic, interactive model within the MID.

Drawing Sequences: For primes 2 and 3, the central pair of complementary divisors of 6, circles are drawn with radii 2 and 3 for $0 \leq n < \infty$ following the formulas:

$$(x - 6n)^2 + y^2 = 2^2$$

$$(x - 12n)^2 + y^2 = 3^2$$

For other primes greater than 3, the sequence $(x - 6Pn)^2 + y^2 = P^2$ is used.

Results:

Figure 21. C001650: Illustrates the Circles producing the Sieve of Prime Numbers in the MID Based on Multiples of 6 (SPM6). See the larger scale figure at the link <https://www.mersenneforum.org/showpost.php?p=647833&postcount=14>.

Visual Representation: The resulting figure illustrates the effectiveness of the SPM6 sieve, showcasing the interaction of these circles with the MID's structure.

Lines Intersection: The diagonal lines $x \pm y = 6$ intersect the X-axis at composite multiples of 6 ($m = 6n = d_1 * d_2$). All circles have their centers on a multiple of 6 along the X-axis. Each circle has a radius equal to the value of one of the divisors d_1 of the multiple of 6. Thus, each circle intersects the X-axis at two points, representing two new composite numbers m' derived from the equations $m' = m \pm d_1$.

Conclusion:

The SPM6 sieve provides a unique, geometric perspective on prime number distribution, leveraging the interplay between prime numbers and the multiples of 6. This method offers a

visually intuitive and mathematically robust approach to understanding prime numbers within the MID.

12 C001651 The MID Circles Sieve of Primes (MCSP): Unveiling the Non-linear Distribution of Prime Divisors

This paragraph examines the innovative MID Circles Sieve of Primes (MCSP) and its unique approach to analyzing prime number distribution within the Map of Integers and Divisors (MID). By starting circle creation from the integer 4, the first positive integer with a divisor greater than 1, the MCSP sieve offers new insights into the non-linear patterns of prime numbers.

The distribution of prime numbers has always been a key focus in number theory. The MCSP sieve provides a fresh perspective by contrasting the linear progression of integers with the complex emergence of prime numbers.

Methodology:

Sieve Foundation: Recognizing the first three positive integers as primes, the sieve initiates circle creation from integer 4.

Circle Centers and Prime Divisors: This approach leads to more circle centers based on prime numbers than typically needed, offering a unique visualization of prime distribution. It highlights the geometric challenge of covering all integers on the number line.

Prime Circles: Each circle is centered at (kP, k) and has a radius k , where P is a prime number and $P \leq k < \infty$. The formula $(x - kP)^2 + (y - k)^2 = k^2$, is crucial for linking circles to prime numbers, providing a geometric representation of their distribution.

Results:

Figure 22. C001651: Illustrates the Circles producing the MID Circles Sieve of Primes (MCSP). See the larger scale figure at the link <https://www.mersenneforum.org/showpost.php?p=647833&postcount=14>.

Insights into Prime Distribution: The surplus of prime-based circle centers in the MCSP sieve emphasizes the non-linear nature of prime number distribution.

Geometric Representation: The formula's application results in a precise geometric mapping of prime numbers, confirming their non-linear distribution and visually encapsulating their mathematical properties.

Conclusion:

The MCSP sieve adds a significant dimension to the study of prime numbers, bridging the gap between abstract number theory and tangible geometric visualization. It highlights the intricate geometric connections within number theory and contributes to a deeper understanding of prime number distribution and characteristics.

13 C001656 The MID Squares Sieve of Primes (MSSP): A Novel Approach to Unveiling the Non-linear Distribution of Primes

This paragraph introduces the MID Squares Sieve of Primes (MSSP), a groundbreaking method within the Map of Integers and Divisors (MID) framework, designed to analyze the distribution of prime numbers and their unique properties.

Prime numbers, key elements in number theory, display distinct distribution patterns. The MSSP method leverages these properties, offering a new lens through which to view prime number distribution.

Methodology:

Sieve Basis: The MSSP is founded on the principle that any integer $x = d_1 \cdot d_2$, when multiplied by one of its divisors other than 1, always results in a multiple of a square number different from 1^2 , as $x \cdot d_2 = d_1 \cdot d_2^2$.

Prime and Composite Numbers: If $x = d_1 \cdot d_2$ is a prime number P , then $d_1 = 1$, $d_2 = P$, and $x \cdot d_2 = P^2$ produces only the square P^2 . For a composite number $x = d_1 \cdot d_2$, there always exists a multiple of some square number of which x is a divisor.

Data Visualization:

Figure 23. C001656: Illustrates the Squares producing the MSSP in the XY-plane, demonstrating the sieve's geometric foundation.

14 C001657 The MID Integers plus Divisors Sieve of Primes (MIPSP) $x + d$ and C001658 The MID Integers minus Divisors Sieve (MIMSP) $x - d$: A Dual Approach to Prime Number Analysis

This paragraph introduces two novel methods within the Map of Integers and Divisors (MID) framework for analyzing prime numbers: The MID Integers plus Divisors Sieve of Primes (MIPSP) $x + d$ and The MID Integers minus Divisors Sieve (MIMSP) $x - d$. These methods utilize both the addition and subtraction of divisors from integers to categorize and understand prime numbers.

Prime numbers, with their unique properties, stand as a cornerstone of number theory. The MIPSP $x + d$ and MIMSP $x - d$ methods provide innovative approaches to identify and categorize prime numbers based on the arithmetic operations of their divisors.

Methodology:

Operational Principles: The MIPSP $x + d$ and MIMSP $x - d$ methods apply the rationale of adding or subtracting divisors from each integer.

Data Visualization:

Figure 23. C001657: $x + d$. See the larger scale figure at the link <https://www.mersenneforum.org/showpost.php?p=647833&postcount=14>.

leading to its appearance four times at the specified heights. This pattern of appearance is consistent with the number of divisors that a given number has, illustrating a fundamental property of the methodology being used to analyze numbers in this context.

Conclusion:

The MIPSP $x + d$ and MIMSP $x - d$ methods offer a comprehensive perspective on prime numbers within the MID framework. By linking each integer with its divisors through both addition and subtraction, these sieves provide a multifaceted approach to distinguishing between primes, composites, and especially square numbers based on their divisor properties.

15 Factory for Record-Breaking Astronomical Prime Numbers: A Methodological Approach Using Oblong Numbers and Large Primorials

This paragraph discusses an innovative method for discovering exceptionally large prime numbers, focusing on the use of oblong numbers derived from large primorials. The approach is based on the conjecture that creating oblong numbers from large primorials significantly increases the likelihood of finding record-breaking prime numbers.

The search for large prime numbers has always been a central topic in number theory. Recent discussions on the Mersenne Forum and studies on primorial numbers suggest a novel approach to identifying astronomical prime numbers.

Methodology:

Conceptual Framework: Drawing on insights from sieves methods and discussions in the Mersenne Forum (<https://www.mersenneforum.org/showthread.php?t=27328>), this study explores the potential of using oblong numbers derived from large primorials (<https://oeis.org/A002110>) for prime number discovery.

Oblong Number Construction: Let 0 be an exceptionally large primorial number. The corresponding oblong number is defined as $x = y(y - 1)$.

Prime Number Search: The method involves testing the following forms for primality:

$$\begin{aligned}x + 1 \\x - 1 \\x + y + 1 \\x - y - 1\end{aligned}$$

Results:

Prime Number Identification: The approach posits that there is a significant possibility of finding at least one prime number among these four forms derived from the oblong number x .

Iterative Process: If none of these numbers are prime, an offset is applied to identify the next oblong number, continuing the search iteratively.

Conclusion:

The concept of using oblong numbers created from large primorials presents a promising avenue for discovering record-breaking prime numbers. This method, combining number theory

principles with a strategic approach to number generation, offers a potentially fast and effective way to identify astronomical prime numbers. The exploration of this method contributes to the ongoing quest to find ever-larger primes, a pursuit that has significant implications in fields such as cryptography and computational mathematics.

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